

TENSILE FAILURE MECHANISM OF UNIDIRECTIONAL PITCH-BASED CFRP WITH DIFFERENT INTERFACIAL STRENGTH

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ABSTRACT

Tensile failure mechanism of unidirectional pitch-based carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) has been experimentally investigated by means of acoustic emission (AE) and electric resistance monitoring. A finite elements method (FEM) has also been applied to simulate the tensile failure process of CFRP. Two kinds of high performance pitch-based carbon fibers have been used for comparative evaluations. It has been shown that the longitudinal tensile strength of unidirectional CFRP is different in spite of the identical mechanical properties of the fibers except an interfacial strength. The observation has showed that a brittle fracture occurs in the CFRP with excessive interfacial strength, while the fracture mode is changed into a cumulative weakening one in CFRP with moderate interfacial strength accompanied with fiber breaking and debonding between fibers and matrix. This difference has been made clear by using AE amplitude analysis, electric resistance change monitoring. And FEM simulation has shown the difference in fracture mechanism of CFRP with different interfacial strength.

INTRODUCTION

Pitch-based carbon fiber has recently been further improved in performance. Especially, high tensile modulus has been attained over 700GPa, which can not be obtained by PAN-based carbon fiber. So that pitch-based carbon fiber is expected to be utilized in the advanced technology fields such as an aerospace. However, the mechanical property of pitch-based CFRP has not been enough clarified compared to PAN-based CFRP. It is widely recognized that the tensile strength of CFRP is influenced significantly by the interfacial strength between fiber and matrix resin in PAN-based carbon fiber. While there have been a few studies concerning the effect of interfacial strength on the tensile property in pitch-based CFRP /1/. It has been reported that the fracture mode changes into the brittle one and the tensile strength decreases by excessive interfacial strength in high modulus pitch-based CFRP. However, the reason has not been made clear enough.

Under this circumstance. in this paper, the tensile failure mechanism of unidirectional pitch-based CFRP with different interfacial strength fibers have been tried to elucidate experimentally and analytically.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

In order to make clear the effect of interfacial strength on the longitudinal tensile strength, two kinds of pitch-based carbon fibers were used for comparative evaluations ; both fibers have the same tensile modulus of about 500GPa and the tensile strength of about 3.5GPa, but one has higher interfacial strength (HM-H) and the other has lower one (HM-L). Those fibers were provided by Toa Nenryo Kogyo Co.,Ltd. for this test.

Figure 1 shows a single fiber embedded specimen to observe the fiber breaking behavior in epoxy resin and to measure the interfacial shear strength /2/. This specimen consists of a single fiber embedded in the surface of epoxy resin, and a tensile load is applied to the fiber by four-point flexure. With increasing axial strain, the fiber is broken into small segments within the matrix. The mean length of segment is known to

be related to the critical fiber length which allows the apparent interfacial shear strength to be calculated with the use of Equation (1).

$$\tau = (\sigma_f \times d) / (2 \times l_c) \quad l_c = 4/3 \times l \quad (1)$$

d: fiber diameter l_c: critical fiber length l: mean length of broken segment
 T: interfacial shear strength σ_f: fiber tensile strength at the length of segment

This equation assumes that the fiber strength is uniform along the length of a fiber/3. Fiber tensile strength at the length of segment cannot be measured directly, so that the strength is calculated from the fiber strength at 25mm and the strength distribution, according to the Weibull statistical estimation.

Fig. 1 Schematic of flexural test of single fiber embedded specimen

Unidirectional CFRP strand specimens were prepared using a conventional method. Carbon fiber tow was impregnated in epoxy resin and was cured at 140°C for two hours. The fiber volume fraction of a specimen was about 50%, but the total of fiber cross-section area was accurately determined from the density of fiber and texture. In order to monitor electric resistance of a strand specimen under tensile loadings, both ends of a strand were polished to expose fiber and an electric conductive painting was applied. Carbon fiber is an electric conductive material while epoxy resin is not, so that fiber breaking behavior in composite can be detected clearly by monitoring the electric resistance change of composite specimen. Aluminum tabs were attached to a specimen in order to use a pin-chuck type joint.

Figure 2 shows a schematic of tensile test of strand specimen. SPARTAN/3000 (PAC) AE monitoring system is used for the tests. AE sensor is μ-30 (PAC), which is small sized and a resonance frequency is 275kHz. The gain of pre-amplifier is 40dB and that of main-amplifier is 20dB. A strand specimen was fastened to a tensile testing machine by a pin-chuck type joint, which is suitable for excluding the mechanical noise from a testing machine. The Kaiser effect was observed by setting the threshold of 40dB, and the Falicity ratio was above 0.95. Two sensors were mounted on a specimen and their calibration were checked by artificial AE source (pencil lead Breaking) for each specimen. The AE amplitude was about 90dB, and the attenuation was less than 5dB between the gauge length of a specimen.

After strand tensile tests, the fracture surface was observed by using scanning electron micrograph.

Fig. 2 Schematic of tensile test of strand specimen

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Table 1 lists the results of single fiber embedded test. Fiber properties are identical in both two fibers except interfacial shear strength. The interfacial shear strength is 43MPa for HM-H fiber, which is more than twice as strong as HM-L fiber.

Figure 3 shows the photoelastic stress patterns in the epoxy matrix near the ends of the broken fiber segment. Fiber break occurs at the strain of 1.1% in HM-L and HM-H, but as the strain is increased to 1.5% or 2.1%, a difference is coming out caused by interfacial strength. In HM-H, the number of fiber break points increase more than in HM-L fiber. The critical fiber length is 0.60mm. With increasing sample strain, an elliptically shaped bright region, which indicates a high shear-stressed part, moves further away from the fiber break ends and leaves a narrow highly stressed region, which looks like a bill of bird. It is considered that the narrow highly stressed region shows the yielding part of matrix resin caused by shear stress. Epoxy resin of the tested specimen is Ep-828/S-CURE, which has about 80MPa of tensile yielding stress. So that, the shear yielding stress is estimated approximately about the same value of interfacial shear strength of HM-M. On the other hand, a different photoelastic stress patterns is observed in HM-L fiber. With the increasing of strain, a bright region spreads along the fiber, and the high magnification microscopic observation shows that fiber debonding is occurred from matrix resin.

Table 1 The results of single fiber embedded tests

Fiber Properties	(unit)	HM-L	HM-H
Density	g/cm ³	2.15	2.15
Diameter	μ m	10	10
Tensile modulus	GPa	500	500
Tensile strength (at 25mm)	GPa	3.5	3.5
Weibull shape parameter		10	10
Critical fiber length	mm	1.26	0.60
Interfacial strength	MPa	19	43

Fig. 3 Polarized microphotographs of fiber break ends
(Three different strain stage of single fiber embedded test)

Table 2 shows the results of longitudinal and transverse tensile strength of composite laminated plates. It is observed that there are some difference between two kinds of CFRP. The longitudinal tensile strength of HM-L is higher about 20% than that of HM-H. And the coefficient of variation (CV) is smaller than that of HM-H. It appears that CFRP with lower interfacial strength has a smaller variation in longitudinal tensile strength. And the transverse tensile strength of laminates is 35MPa for HM-L, 50MPa for HM-H.

Table 2 The results of strand tests

Composite properties	(unit)	HM-L	HM-H
Number of filaments	K	6	6
Cross section area of strand specimen	mm ²	0.43	0.43
Tensile strength of strand (CV)	GPa %	3.5 1.3	2.8 4.2
Initial electric resistance (Ri)	ohm	5.0	5.0
Increase of electric resistance (dR)	ohm	0.10	0.05
Increase ratio of electric resistance at failure	%	2.0	1.0
Transverse tensile strength	MPa	35	50

Figure 4 shows the AE measured results of strand specimens with a point plot, and Fig.5 shows the electric resistance change and the fiber strength distribution curve $f(x)$ at 25mm length. The AE amplitude of fiber break is high, which is about 80dB for high modulus pitch-based carbon fiber /4/. The results of HM-H show that the observed AE amplitude increases with stress; a high amplitude over 80dB is observed from strand stress 2.5GPa while the strand failure stress is 2.8GPa. The point at which the electric resistance and the fiber failure probability increase rapidly are almost coincident at the stress of 2.5GPa. In the case of HM-L, AE amplitude and electric resistance at the same stress appears to be similar to HM-H. However, the failure stress of HM-L is higher than that of HM-H. At the stress of above 2.8GPa, many high amplitude AE signals are observed and electric resistance increases more rapidly.

Fig. 4 AE amplitude versus stress

Fig. 5 Electric resistance change and Weibull distribution curve

Figure 6 shows the SEM observation of strand fracture surface. A significant difference is observed between the two kinds of CFRP. The fracture surface of HM-H is relatively smooth, and fiber pull out is not observed with a few exceptions, which looks like a brittle fracture surface. On the other hand, many fiber pull out is observed in HM-L fracture surface. And the fracture occurred at the surface of fiber and matrix resin.

Fig. 6 SEM observation of fracture surface

FINITE ELEMENT METHOD SIMULATIONS

The statistical nature of tensile failure process of UD CFRP was characterized by means of the finite element method (FEM) simulations. The model consists of isoparametric finite elements : 21 x 8 fiber elements and 20 x 8 matrix elements which are connected by normal and shear spring elements between adjoining two nodes. The material constants of fiber and matrix are assumed as shown in Table 3. The strength of fiber elements is allotted based on the Weibull distribution. The interfacial strength is assumed to be 50MPa for HM-L and 100MPa for HM-H. The dynamic failure process was simulated by breaking spring elements one by one based on a load increment scheme.

The results of simulations are listed in Table 4, and the typical examples of failure patterns of models are showed in Fig.7. The results indicates that the mean tensile strength is larger and variation of tensile strength is smaller in HM-L than HM-H. This agrees very well with the experimental results in tendency. And the simulated failure patterns of composite are also coincident with the fracture surface of SEM observation.

Table 3 Material constant for simulation

	Fiber	Matrix
Tensile modulus	400 GPa	3.5 GPa
Tensile strength	3.5 GPa	0.12 GPa
Weibull shape parameter	6.98	—

Table 4 The results of FEM simulation

	50 MPa	100 MPa
Interfacial strength		
Mean tensile strength of compos	2.39 Gpa	1.99 GPa
C.V of tensile strenth	7.4 %	12.1 %

Fig. 7 Typical simulated failure patterns of CFRP models

DISCUSSION

To judge the tensile failure mechanism of CFRP by putting together AE, electric resistance monitoring, SEM observations and FEM simulations, fiber breaking behavior in composites is independent of interfacial strength, while the composite strength of HM-L is higher than that of HM-H. It is considered that the failure of HM-H is a fiber break propagation mode, but HM-L is a cumulative weakening mode. The initial stage of those two modes are shown to be identical /5/. Hence the AE characteristic and electric resistance are similar in HM-L and HM-H at the same stress level. But as the stress increases, first fiber break tends to cause sequentially adjacent fiber breaks in HM-H. And the fracture surface of HM-H looks like a brittle one. It suggests that the excessive interfacial strength is not desirable for the composite tensile strength of pitch-based CFRP.

CONCLUSIONS

The tensile failure mechanism of unidirectional CFRP has been characterized. The results are summarized as follows:

- (1) The fracture of CFRP with moderate interfacial strength can be a cumulative weakening mode accompanied with fiber debonding.
- (2) However, the fracture mode tends to change into a fiber break propagation mode when the interfacial strength is excessive.
- (3) Hence it is considered that the excessive interfacial strength is not desirable for the composite tensile strength of pitch-based CFRP.

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